

Impact of Corruption on Money Laundering

Axmadaliyeva Nihola
Tashkent State University of Economics, Teacher
axmadaliyevanihola@gmail.com

Raxmatov Mirshod
Tashkent State University of Economics
Student of Finance faculty
raxmatovmirshod21@gmail.com

Annotation: This thesis explores the intricate relationship between corruption and money laundering, two pervasive phenomena that threaten the integrity of financial systems worldwide. Corruption, often defined as the abuse of entrusted power for private gain, has been identified as a significant facilitator of money laundering activities. Through an interdisciplinary approach drawing from criminology, economics, and political science, this study aims to dissect the mechanisms through which corruption fuels money laundering and its subsequent socio-economic impacts.

Keywords: financial crimes, corruption, money laundering, transactions, legitimate, tax evasion, bribery, economic growth, payments, anti-money laundering

In the world of financial crimes worldwide, corruption and money laundering are closely linked and create big problems for the economy, governance, and society. Corruption is when people misuse their power for personal gain, and money laundering is how illegal money is hidden. These two are connected and part of illegal financial activities. To fight these problems effectively, it's crucial to understand how corruption and money laundering are connected.

Money laundering is the act of hiding the source of "dirty money," or money obtained illegally, and pretending that it was acquired lawfully. Corrupt politicians frequently use this technique to conceal their assets and money that they have either stolen or obtained illegally. Globally speaking, money laundering has become a major issue, but it is particularly prevalent in nations where corrupt activities are more prevalent.⁵

⁵ <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/m/moneylaundering.asp>

Money laundering is the practice of concealing the source of assets or funds through a series of complex transactions. These transactions usually involve dividing up big amounts of money into smaller amounts so they can be transferred more quickly and easily, hiding the money's true source, and then changing the assets' or money's form to conceal where they really came from. The purpose of money laundering is to provide a criminal or corrupt politician with a "legitimate" source of income in order to evade detection by regulatory agencies and law enforcement⁶.

Money laundering is often intertwined with corruption and various illegal activities like bribery, tax evasion, and trafficking. Corrupt politicians commonly use money laundering to conceal their wrongdoing and amass illegal assets. This "black money" obtained through corruption is then hidden through money laundering, enabling the acquisition of property, luxury items, and illicit services.

The connection between corruption and money laundering has big effects on the world's economies, rules, and legal systems. When corrupt practices lead to illegal money flows, it hurts economic growth, creates unfair competition, and reduces people's trust in institutions. This cycle of corruption and financial crime keeps repeating. Additionally, dealing with money laundering is hard because of its links to corruption, making it challenging to follow rules, cooperate internationally, and prevent financial crimes. Statistics show that the estimated amount of money laundered a year is 2-5% of global GDP or 800-2 trillion US dollars.

Corrupt practices have been around for more than 2000 years, so they are not a new phenomenon. Numerous historical examples of ancient kingdoms were characterized by widespread corruption. Corruption is a much more widespread phenomenon that is only visible to the observer and dependent on how the act is perceived. On the other hand, a number of academics have defined corruption as deliberate noncompliance in a transaction that grants an advantage to an individual or group of individuals. Simply, corruption can happen when someone abuses their position of authority for personal benefit. The World Bank estimates that 10% of global GDP, or roughly \$8 trillion

⁶ <https://www.acamstoday.org/corruption-money-laundering-and-the-economy/>

annually, is involved in corruption. This astounding amount emphasizes the enormous amount of money lost as a result of corrupt practices.

The four primary types of corruption are fraud, extortion, embezzlement, and bribery. Nevertheless, there may be overlaps and similarities between these types of corruption and others, like theft, nepotism, and favoritism. Public officials are typically the ones who commit corruption. For example, a state elected official may accept payments in exchange for awarding a particular state contract, or an elected official may mix public funds for personal gain. Other instances include blackmailing or using coercion to extract money in order to defraud the government by underreporting taxes. The Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) for 2022 by Transparency International rates nations from 0 (very corrupt) to 100 (very clean), with the depressingly low global average score of 43 continuing to point to a widespread issue. Where Uzbekistan was on the 121th place with the result of 31, and the other Central Asian countries like Turkmenistan, Tajikistan and Kazakhstan scored 18, 20 and 39 respectively. ⁷

Corruption in public is regarded as a federal offense. Thus, bribing a public official is considered a criminal act not only by the one receiving the bribe but also by the one offering the bribe. Moreover, bribery is one of the two specific offenses listed in the U.S. Constitution that can result in a president's impeachment. Since corruption is viewed as a white-collar crime, it occasionally receives preferential treatment from the legal system over violent crimes. Compared to violent crime, white-collar crime is viewed differently and is treated differently. It is often this fascinating phenomenon that white-collar crimes bring to the table that results in these types of offenses being treated differently by the public.

For instance, it is common practice in some nations (primarily in developing nations) to bribe public officials in order to expedite the performance of those government offices or to get a routine service completed. In situations like this, the degree of corruption is determined by the moral struggle and the individual's perception. Sometimes it is more difficult to identify the victims and perpetrators of embezzlement, which makes

⁷ [2023 Corruption Perceptions Index: Explore the... - Transparency.org](#)

it more difficult to prosecute the offenders. Since the perpetrators and victims are usually easily identified, violent crimes are frequently easier to prosecute.

While corruption is universally illegal, enforcement against offenders can vary due to legal and political factors. Money laundering involves concealing unlawfully obtained funds, with corrupt gains transferred through different channels, including financial institutions or unofficial means. To evade detection, corrupt funds are often moved to tax havens. However, stringent penalties under anti-money laundering (AML) laws make it more effective to prosecute those who connect corruption to money laundering offenses.

Anti-Money Laundering (AML) is a crucial tool in preventing money laundering, which involves the transformation of illicit funds into lawful assets. AML strategies involve strict requirements on financial institutions, including the "Know Your Customer" (KYC) principle, which requires them to verify customer identities and understand their funds' sources. AML also involves thorough monitoring of transactions for suspicious activity. Upon detecting suspicious activity, AML regulations require institutions to report it to authorities, enabling law enforcement to investigate potential money laundering schemes and disrupt illicit financial flows. Money laundering typically unfolds in three stages: placement, layering, and integration. Effective AML implementation requires robust programs, employee training, and regular risk assessments. International cooperation among financial institutions, law enforcement, and regulators is essential for combating money laundering globally.